

unavailable. Tillage with cultivators and disk harrows varies from two to five times. We evaluated the cultivator, disk harrow, and rotary puddler for rice cultivation (see table).

Results indicate that

1. It takes more time to puddle with a disk harrow than with a cultivator or rotary puddler, presumably because the harrow has a higher draft requirement.
2. With only one tilling, a rotary blade puddler decreases infiltration rate most to 15 mm/d.
3. A second tilling with a harrow or cultivator further reduces the infiltration rate. One or two tillings with the rotary blade puddler

Performance of various tractor-drawn puddlers in Kaul, India.

	Cultivator		Paddy disk harrow		Rotary blade puddler		CD 5%
	Single operation	Double operation	Single operation	Double operation	Single operation	Double operation	
Puddling time (h/ha)	2.9	4.9	4.0	6.7	3.6	5.8	
Puddling cost (\$/ha)	17	29	24	40	22	35	
Infiltration rate (mm/d)	19	14	15	8	15	15	
Yield (t/ha)	4.2	4.3	3.9	4.5	3.8	3.9	0.075
Hills/m ²	36.8	36	37	36.2	36.2	36.3	
Panicles/hill	8.5	8.2	8.5	8.8	8.2	8.0	
Grains/panicle	110	113	113	125	112	114	8.5
1000-grain mass (g)	28.5	29.6	28.0	28.3	29.7	30.7	1.8

4. Two cultivator tillings produce an infiltration rate similar to that from one tilling with a rotary blade

5. The twice harrow-puddled field had lowest infiltration and yielded most. ∞

Effect of irrigation scheduling and nitrogen application on rice yield

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We studied the effect of four water regimes and three N levels and their interactions on rice yield (see table). The water regimes were imposed during a dry spell in mid-Sep 1984.

Crop water use was 1294 mm (see figure), of which 32% was used in vegetative phase, 45% in reproductive

Weekly rainfall and rate of water use (mm)

Rate of water use at different rice growth stages, Raipur, India.

Effect of irrigation and applied N levels on rice yield, Raipur, India.

Water regime ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	No N	40 kg/ha	80 kg/ha
T1	2.5	3.2	4.2
T2	2.5	3.3	3.7
T3	2.5	3.3	3.9
T4	2.5	3.3	3.8
CD	5%	1%	
N level significance	0.1	0.2	
Water level not significant	—	—	
Interaction significance	0.2	0.3	

^a T1-T4 received 5 cm irrigation water when groundwater level was at the indicated depth (in parentheses).

phase, and 23% during ripening. Rainfall met crop water demand until the vegetative phase. Five cm of irrigation water was applied when the groundwater table receded to 0 (T1), 10 (T2), 20 (T3), or 30 cm (T4). Total water use was 1294 mm at T1, 1110 at T2, 1067 at T3, and 927 mm at T4. Water regime did not significantly affect yield (see table), suggesting that continuous submergence is not necessary to produce high yield and that water use efficiency may be greater with a period of drainage between irrigations.

T1 with 80 kg N/ha produced significantly higher yields than the other treatment combinations, suggesting the need for continuous submergence at higher N application levels for good crop

response to fertilizer. Lack of submergence during reproductive stage reduced the yield benefits under high N application. N level may be important to rice field water management. ∞

Growth depression of blue-green algae (BGA) in lowland fields on the Godavari Delta

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BGA blooms do not develop in Godavari Delta rice fields even with inoculation (algalization). Some possible reasons for failure, obtained mainly from